

10.5281/zenodo.4301412

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:4D544226-C8C3-4717-91DB-9C7AEF420790

The new records of the short-winged mold beetles (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) from the Dvorichansky National Park

R. E. Krivosheyev

I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology
National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Bogdan Chmielnitski St. 15/2,
01030 Kyiv, Ukraine

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-7319-1205>E-mail: accipitergentilis777@gmail.com

Krivosheyev, R. E. The new records of the short-winged mold beetles (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) from the Dvorichansky National Park. — Thirteen species of Pselaphinae are collected from the Dvorichansky National Park. Of them, eleven are recorded for the first time from Kharkiv Region.

Key words: Ukraine, Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Pselaphinae, Dvorichansky National Park, new records.

Кривошесєв Р. Є. Нові знахідки жуків-потаємців (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) на території Дворічанського національного парку. У Дворічанському національному парку знайдено 13 видів потаємців. З них, 11 вперше зазначено для Харківської області.

Ключові слова: Україна, Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Pselaphinae, Дворічанський національний парк, нові знахідки.

Introduction

The subfamily Pselaphinae was known to be represented by 126 species of 25 genera in the fauna of Ukraine (Krivosheyev, 2015). In Kharkiv Region, Pselaphines theretofore were mentioned only in the publication of Krynicki (1832), with only two species in it: *Pselaphus heisei* (Herbst, 1792), and *Rybaxis longicornis* (Leach, 1817). During a collecting trip to Dvorichansky National Park, additional 11 species of the 8 genera of Pselaphinae were collected in litter on the chalk slopes of Oskol River and in the deciduous forest nearby. In addition, the private collection of Oleg Novikov was defined. All these species are first recorded from Kharkiv region. *Bryaxis chaudoirii* (Chaudoir, 1845) known only to the west of Ukraine (Krivosheyev, 2018) is recorded from Kharkiv Region for the first time. All material collected by the author is deposited in the collection of I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, Kyiv (SIZK).

Euplectus bonvouloiri naretinus Reitter, 1881 (Fig. 1)

Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 284.

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichansky National Park: deciduous forest n. Krasne, 5-6.05.2019, 49.9498 N, 37.7603 E, 3 specimens (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Central and South-Eastern Europe (Loebl, 2004).

Fig. 1. *Euplectus bonvouloiri naretinus* ♂ habitus dorsal

Notes. In dead wood in litter, often with ants (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Biblopectus spinosus Raffray, 1914

Winkler 1925: 452; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 291.

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichanskiy National Park: dry chalk hills, in litter, 30.04–4.05.2020, 49.9634 N, 37.8126 E, 4 ♂, 6 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK); *ibid.*, deciduous forest n. Krasne, 5-6.05.2019, 49.9498 N, 37.7603 E, 6 ♂, 3 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe, excluding South (Loebl, 2004).

Notes. The species occur in moss, grass and deciduous forest litter along the riverbanks, swamps and lakes (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Trimium brevicorne (Reichenbach, 1816)

Winkler 1925: 449; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 293.

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichanskiy National Park: Krasne, in litter, 4.08.2015, 1 ♀ (Novikov leg.).

Distribution. Europe, excl. South (Loebl, 2004).

Notes. In litter, dead wood, and anthills (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Amauronyx maerkeli (Aubé, 1844) (fig. 2)

Winkler 1925: 452; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 293.

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichanskiy National Park: deciduous forest n. Krasne, 5-6.05.2019, 49.9498 N, 37.7603 E, 4 specimens (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe, excl. Mediterranean and North (Loebl, 2004).

Notes. Under the bark and in litter, often with ants (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Fig. 2. *Amauronyx maerkeli*, habitus dorsal.

Batrisodes venustus (Reichenbach, 1816)

Winkler 1925: 454; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 278.

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichanskiy National Park: deciduous forest n. Krasne, under the pine bark with ants, 5-6.05.2019, 49.9498 N, 37.7603 E, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost the whole of Europe (Loebl, 2004).

Notes. Myrmecophylous species, occurs under the bark (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Brachygluta fossulata (Reichenbach, 1816)

Winkler, 1925: 455; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 297.

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichanskiy National Park: dry chalk hills, in litter, 30.04–4.05.2020, 49.9634 N, 37.8126 E, 20 specimens (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK); *ibid.*, deciduous forest n. Krasne, 5-6.05.2019, 49.9498 N, 37.7603 E, 3 specimens (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost whole Europe (Loebl, 2004).

Notes. Common species of the forest litter, moss and occasionally under the tree bark (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Brachygluta sinuata (Aubé, 1833)

Winkler 1925: 457; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 299.

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichanskiy National Park: dry chalk hills, in litter, 30.04–4.05.2020, 49.9634 N, 37.8126 E, 4 ♂, 7 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost whole Europe (Loebl, 2004).

Notes. In litter near the freshwater banks and in moist places (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1996).

Brachygluta haematica (Reichenbach, 1816)

Winkler 1925: 455; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 297.

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichanskiy National Park: dry chalk hills, in litter, 30.04–4.05.2020, 49.9634 N, 37.8126 E, 2 ♂ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost whole of Europe (Loebl, 2004).

Notes. In litter of the forests and wet meadows, sometimes in moss and under the bark (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Rybaxis longicornis (Leach, 1817)

Winkler 1925: 458; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 300.

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichanskiy National Park: dry chalk hills, in litter, 30.04–4.05.2020, 49.9634 N, 37.8126 E, 5 specimens (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK); *ibid.*, deciduous forest n. Krasne, 5-6.05.2019, 49.9498 N, 37.7603 E, 1 specimen (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe excl. North (Loebl, 2004).

Notes. In litter, silt and rotting grass (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bryaxis bulbifer (Reichenbach, 1816)

Winkler, 1925: 461; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 304.

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichanskiy National Park: dry chalk hills, in litter, 30.04–4.05.2020, 49.9634 N, 37.8126 E, 16 ♂, 18 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK); *ibid.*, deciduous forest n. Krasne, 5-6.05.2019, 49.9498 N, 37.7603 E, 23 ♂, 23 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost whole of Europe (Loebl, 2004).

Notes. The species lives in forest litter near the water, in moss and under the stones (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

***Bryaxis chaudiarii* (Chaudoir, 1845) (Fig. 3)**

Winkler 1925: 460; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 304.

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichansky National Park: dry chalk hills, in litter, 30.04–4.05.2020, 49.9634 N, 37.8126 E, 8 ♂, 7 ♀ (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Eastern Europe and Balkans (Loebl, 2004).

Notes. Xerophytic species, lives on dry steppe slopes in moss under the trees (Krivosheyev, 2015, 2018).

Fig. 3. *Bryaxis chaudiarii*, ♂ habitus dorsal

***Ctenistes palpalis* (Reichenbach, 1816)**

Winkler 1925: 468; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 321.

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichansky National Park: meadow, at light, 7.08.2015, 1 ♂ (Novikov leg.).

Distribution. Europe, excl. Great Britain, Poland and Scandinavia (Loebl, 2004).

Notes. Xerophytic species, dwells exceptionally in the nests of the ants *Tetramorium caespitum* (Linnaeus, 1758).

***Pselaphus heisei* (Herbst, 1792)**

Winkler 1925: 466; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 327

Material examined. Ukraine, Kharkiv Region, Dvorichansky National Park: dry chalk hills, in litter, 30.04–4.05.2020, 49.9634 N, 37.8126 E, 5 specimens (Krivosheyev leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost whole Europe (Loebl, 2004).

Notes. The species lives in rotting grass, under the bark, in moss and moist forest litter, often near the banks of rivers and lakes (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Aknowledgements

I greatly appreciate generous help of Oleg Novikov and Maksym Vysochyn for their invaluable assistance during the trip. I thank Kateryna Martynova and Valery Korneyev (I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology) for their assistance and advices for the microphotography.

References

- Jeannel, R., 1950. Coléoptères Pselaphides. *Faune de France*. Paris, 53: 1–422.
- Krivosheyev, R. 2015. The short-winged mold beetles (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) of Ukraine (fauna, zoogeography, morphological and ecological peculiarities). Manuscript of PhD thesis. Available at <http://docplayer.net/65615500-Krivosheiev-robert-ievgenovich.html> (in Ukrainian).
- Krivosheyev, R. 2018. The new records of the short-winged mold beetles (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) from the Dnistrovskiy Canyon National Park. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka*, 9 (4): 1–4.
- Krynicky, I. 1832. Enumeratio Coleopterorum Rossiae meridionalis et praecipue in Universitatis Caesariae Charkoviensis circulo obvenientium, quae annorum 1827–1831 spatio observavit. *Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou*, 5: 178.
- Löbl, I. 2004. Pselaphinae. In: Löbl, I. & Besuchet, C. (eds.). *Catalogue of Palearctic Coleoptera*. Vol. 2. Apollo Books, Stenstrup: 272–329.
- Loebl, I. 2013. Fauna Europaea: Pselaphinae. In: Alonso-Zarazaga M. *Fauna Europaea: Coleoptera, Staphylinidae*. *Fauna Europaea version 2017.06*, <https://fauna-eu.org>
- Neuhäuser-Happe, L. 1995. Verbreitung und Ökologie der Palpenkäfer in Kärnten und den angrenzenden Gebieten (Pselaphidae, Coleoptera). *Carinthia II*, 185/105: 735–772.
- Neuhäuser-Happe, L. 1996. Zur Verbreitung und Ökologiewenig bekannter und seltener Palpenkäfer in der Steiermark (Pselaphidae, Coleoptera). *Mitteilungen des Naturwissenschaftlichen Vereines für Steiermark*, 126: 189–213.
- Winkler, A. 1925. *Pselaphidae. Catalogus coleopterorum regionis palaearticae*. Albert Winkler, Wien, 4: 448–471.